

A Descriptive Study to Assess the Knowledge Regarding Diarrhea among the Mother of Under Five Children at Kansa Village

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ABSTRACT: The Primary Ailment In Children Under The Age Of Five Is Diarrhea. Around 1.5 Million Children Die From Diarrhoea Each Year, With Asia Accounting For 38% Of All Deaths. In India, There Are Over 2 Million Cases Of Diarrhea Each Year. Children Between The Ages Of 28 Days And 5 Years: 6.6 Million Deaths The Purpose Of This Descriptive Study Was To Gauge The Mothers Of Young Children In Kansa Village's Knowledge Of Diarrhea. No probability Purposive Sampling Technique Included 30 Mothers Of Children Under The Age Of Five. The Study's Findings Show That 23 (76.66 Percent) Of The Mothers Of Children Under Five Had Somewhat Adequate Knowledge About Diarrhea, With 4 (13.33 Percent) Having Adequate Knowledge And 3 (10%) Having Insufficient Knowledge. Significant Correlations Were Found Between Socio demographic Factors And Mothers' Knowledge. Age, Types Of Family, Occupation Of Mother, Education Of Mother, Varieties Of House And Types Of Health Resources Used. The Study Concluded That, Most Of Mothers Of Kansa Village Require Awareness Regarding Diarrhea And Its Management.

KEYWORDS: Diarrhea, Knowledge of Fewer than Five Children Mother, Under Five Children.

BACKGROUND OF STUDY

India, Diarrhoea May Even Be A Serious Killer Disease That Affects Children Under The Age Of Five, Making It A Critically Important Public Health Issue. Delay In The Start Of Treatment And Inadequate Hydration In High Morbidity Are The Causes Of The Alarming Situation. In The World, Diarrheal Disease Is The Second Most Common Cause Of Death In Children Under The Age Of Five. Children Are Our Most Valuable Resources And Essential For Our Future. In Other Words, The Children Are The State's Future Citizens And Future Human Resources. Children Who Are In Good Health Don't Just Seem To Be Assets; They Also Seem To Be The Foundation Of A Strong And Prosperous Nation. A Prerequisite For The Development Of Humanity Is Their Survival, Protection, And Advancement. Protecting Children's Health And Development Is Also A Terrible Future. Given That Children Make Up One-Third Of The Total Population, It Is Imperative To Assess The Health Of Children In The Nation. Additionally, Child Care Is A Crucial Issue Because Children Are Most At Risk For Malnutrition, Morbidity, And Mortality. India J Child Health (Bhopal) Acute Diarrhoea Accounts For An Outsized Burden Of Infectious Diseases Inunder-Fivechildren. Eastern Odisha, India Although India Has Steadily Reduced The Number Of Children Under The Age Of Five Who Pass Away, The Proportion Of Deaths Attributable To Diarrheal Diseases Is Still High. This Hospital-Based Cross-Sectional Study Was Conducted To Understand The Prevalence Of Several Bacterial Pathogens Linked To Diarrhoea Cases In Children Under The Age Of Five.

Laura M Lamberti,Christa L Fischer Walker & Robert E Black BMC Public Health (2012) Article Number:276diarrhea Is Additionally Variety One Explanation For Morbidity And Mortality Across All Age Groups And Regions Of The World. Among Children 0-59 Months Old, Diarrhea Is Responsible For 1.236 Million Deaths Annually And Is That the Second Leading Explanation for Death During This People. Though Mortality Rates Among Older Children, Adolescents, And Adults Are Under Those Observed In Children Under Five, Diarrhea Still Poses A Substantial Burden Accounting For About 2.8 Billion Diarrhea Episodes Among Older Children, Adolescents, And Adults.

HailemariamMekonnenWorkie , Diarrhea Remains The 2nd Leading Reason For Death Among Children Under 5 Globally. It Kills More Young Children Than AIDS. It'd Are Prevented By Simple Home Management Using Oral Rehydration Therapy. Mother Has

To Know About Its Management And Prevention. So, The Foremost Objective Of This Study Was To Assess Mothers’ Knowledge, Attitude & Practice In Prevention & Home-Based Management Of Diarrheal Disease Among Under-Five Children In Dire Dawa, Eastern Ethiopia.

METHODOLOGY

The Investigation Was Conducted In Survey Setting at Kansa Village Is the Location of the Study. The Study's Research Design is A Descriptive Research Design. The Mother Of Under Five Children Are Chose Using A Nonprobability Sampling Technique. For This Trial, 30 Mother Of Under Five Children Are Chose And They Are Given Self Administered Knowledge Questionnaire. Questionnaire Is To Assess The Knoeledge Of Mother Of Under Five Children Regarding Diarrohea In Kansa Village. It Consists Of 20 Items Of Multiple Choice Questions Total Score Is 20. The Data Is Evaluated With Descriptive And Interstitial Statistics Like Mean, SD, And The Chi-Square Test.

RESULT

The Result Have Been Organized And Presented In Following Headings:

Table 1: Sample Frequency and Percentage Distribution Based on Demographic Characteristics.

S. No	Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
1	Age	18-21yr.	17	56.66%
		21-24yr	06	20%
		24-25yr	02	6.66%
		25 Above	05	16.66s%
2.	Type Of Family	Joint	25	83.33 %
		Nuclear	05	16.66%
3.	Occupations Of Mother	House Wife	12	40 %
		Business	08	26.66%
		Government Job	09	30%
		Private Job	01	3.33%
4.	Education Of Mother	Primary Education	19	63.33%
		Higher Secondary Education	06	20 %
		Degree Holder	04	13.33 %
		Illiterate	01	3.33%
5.	Monthly Income	3000	17	56.66%
		3000-4000	06	20 %
		4000-5000	02	6.66%
		5000 Above	05	16.66%
6.	Types Of House	Paved Building	20	66.66%
		B-Raw Building	09	30 %
		Hut	01	3.33%
7	Source Of Water	Well Water	03	10%
		Tap Water	27	90%
		Hand Pump	00	00%
8	Number Of Children	1	09	30%
		2	18	60%
		3	03	10%
		>3	00	00%

9	Types Of Health Resources Used	Government Hospital	22	73.33%
		Private Hospitals	07	23.33%
		Home Remedies	01	3.33%
10	Religion	Hindu	29	96.66%
		Muslim	01	3.33%
		Christian	00	56.66%
		Others	00	20%

Table 2: An Analysis of Knowledge Score of Mothers of Under Five Children on Diarrhea. This section deals with the analysis and interpretation of the data regarding knowledge score being summarized using frequency and percentage. N=30

Knowledge score	Knowledge score	
	frequency	percentage
0 -8(Inadequate)	03	10%
9 to 15 (Moderately adequate)	23	76.66%
15-20(Adequate)	04	13.33%
Total	30	100%

The data presented in the table 2 and Figure 1 depicts that the majority of the respondents 23(76.66%) had moderately adequate knowledge on diarrhea, 4(13.44%) had adequate knowledge and 3(10%) had inadequate knowledge on diarrhea.

Figure-1 Level Of Knowledge Of Mother Of Under Five Year Children Regarding Diarrhoea.

Table 3: Mean, S.D, And Significance Level Of Knowledge Of Diarrohea Among The Mothers Of Under Five Years Children.

PARAMETERS	MEAN	S D	LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANCE 0.05
LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE	11.46	3.08	S

Table 3 Shows That The Average Pre Test Scores On The Level Of Knowledge Of Diarrohea Among The Mother Of Under-five Year Children Mean Score Is 11.46 (SD 3.08). There Was Significant Association Between Knowledge Of Mothers And Demographic Variables Like Age, Types Of Family, Occupation Of Mother, Education Of Mother, Types Of House And Types Of Health Resources Used.

Table 4: The relationship between level of knowledge and selected demographic characteristics among under five year children mothers.

Sr. No	Variable	Category	Frequency	percentage	Inadequate	Moderately adequate	Adequate	DF	T value	Chi square	Significant P value
1	Age	18-21yr.	17	56.66%	00	16	01	6	2.31	13.63	0.03 S
		21-24yr	06	20%	01	03	02				
		24-25yr	02	6.66%	01	00	01				
		25 Above	05	16.66s%	01	4	00				
2.	Type of family	Joint	25	83.33 %	02	22	01	2	22.32	12.9	0.001 S
		Nuclear	05	16.66%	01	01	03				
3.	Occupations of mother	House wife	12	40 %	00	10	02	6	2.61	14.6	0.02 S
		Business	08	26.66%	02	06	00				
		Government job	09	30s%	00	07	02				
		Private job	01	3.33%	01	00	00				
4.	Education of mother	Primary education	19	63.33%	02	17	00	6	3.142	16.45	0.01 S
		Higher secondary education	06	20 %	00	05	01				
		Degree holder	04	13.33 %	00	01	02				
		Illiterate	01	3.33%	00	00	01				
5.	Monthly income	3000	17	56.66%	01	15	01	6	0.02	5.37	0.49 NS
		3000-4000	06	20 %	01	03	02				
		4000-5000	02	6.66%	00	02	00				

		5000 above	05	16.66%	01	03	01				
6.	Types of house	Paved building	20	66.66%	03	17	00	4	2.99	11.60	0.02 S
		B-raw building	09	30 %	00	05	04				
		hut	01	3.33%	00	01	00				
7	Source of water	Well water	03	10%	00	02	01	2	0.81	1.37	0.50 NS
		Tap water	27	90%	03	21	03				
		Hand pump	00	00%	00	00	00				
8	Number of children	1	09	30%	02	06	01	4	0.74	3.26	0.5 NS
		2	18	60%	01	15	02				
		3	03	10%	00	02	01				
		>3	00	00%	00	00	00				
9	Types of health resources used	Government hospital	22	73.33%	03	18	01	4	2.60	10.08	0.03 S
		Private hospitals	07	23.33%	00	05	02				
		Home remedies	01	3.33%	00	00	01				
10	religion	Hindu	29	96.66%	03	22	04	2	1.38	0.31	0.85 NS
		Muslim	01	3.33%	00	01	00				
		Christian	00	00%	00	00	00				
		others	00	00%	00	00	00				

DISCUSSION

Present Study Results Depicts That the majority 23(76.66%) Mothers Of Under Five Children Had Moderately Adequate Knowledge On Diarrhea, Remaining 4(13.33%) Mothers Had Adequate Knowledge And 3(10%) Had Inadequate Knowledge. The Calculated Chi Square Values Were Less Than Table Value & Checked At The Quantity Of 0.05 Level. There A Giant Association Between Knowledge Score Of Mother Of Under Five Children & Selected Demographic Variables Like Age, Types of Family , Occupation Of Mother , Education Of Mother , types of House and sorts of Health Resources Used.

A Similar Study Was Carried Out At The Government Medical College And Hospital In Chandigarh To Evaluate The Knowledge Of Mothers Of Children Under The Age Of Five Regarding The Treatment Of Diarrhea. According To The Study's Findings, Out Of 260 Subjects, 23% Had Good Knowledge, 73% Had Average Knowledge, And 4% Had Poor Knowledge Of How To Treat Diarrhea In Children Under The Age Of Five. There Was A Correlation Between Legal Status And Knowledge Score. The Study Found That The Majority Of Mothers Of Children Under Five Had Average Knowledge On How To Manage Diarrhea.

CONCLUSION

From The Present Study, The Results Revealed That The Majority 23(76.66%) Of The Mother Of Under Five Children Had Moderately Adequate Knowledge On Diarrhea, Remaining 4(13.33%) Mothers Had Adequate Knowledge And 3(10%) Had Inadequate Knowledge.

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